
Impact of Social Media on Consumer Culture

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ABSTRACT

The socio-economic mechanism of consumerism is driven by technological dynamics which brings significant impact in the interest for both mankind and economies. Thus, it is important to take note on how people give reaction to different objects and materials according to changing consummation and market scenario. The use of social media has even broadened the style and process of consumption culture. Consumers are now more conscious about product differentiation hence facilitated a new culture of participation and interaction among individuals. Moreover, the increase in virtual communities is leading towards empowerment of consumers. In this study the role of social media and its dynamic properties are discussed along with the impact on consumer culture, propensity to consumer and buying behavior. The various aspects of product development, promotion and innovative creation and manufacturing in conjunction with the enablement of social media addictive technologies is also highlighted through various examples and graphs. This research article elaborates the influence of social media on the design and production of products of the next generation to attract hence enhances the purchase as well as search of the product serve on the new media platforms.

Introduction

Nowadays, consumers are knowledgeable and can also contribute towards innovation in production and assist in creating opportunities by voicing their opinion through various social media platforms such as blogs, videos, crowd funding for a particular product and by the means of other AI assistive techniques. Therefore, this paper also emphasizes the factors that are responsible for changes in consumer behavior and healthy customer- organization relationship by the means of social media. The economic theory of propensity to consume also express habit of purchase, collecting, consumption and investment on commodity or delightful for economic materialism and emphasize policies for rational consumption. The individualistic ideology advocates rational consumption in consecutive way and also suggest to follow the theory of opportunity cost where one has to sacrifice their next best alternative.

In consumer sovereignty era, consumer is king and have power to affect the market forces of demand and supply. They can also mold and fold the market. Takin into consideration the producer must keep marketing mix in streamline to meet consumer satisfaction level and economic goal of the company.

To remain on same position a marketer has to run faster than the competitors. Since consumers have freedom of choices hence what to produce (luxurious or necessity goods), how to produce (method, process and technology), for whom to produce (target customer) and breaking the large monolithic market. Segmentation is crucial decision for placing a product in the market to meet likes, teste, habit, preferences and passion of customers leads growth of product as well as company.

Review of literature

The term social media cannot be isolated from the concept of Web 2.0 (World Wide Web) a place of continuous operation, sharing of contents among the operators in a collaborative manner (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). The information on social media is persistently shared, operated and consumed among the users (Campbell et al, 2011). The evolution of Web 2.0 arose from simple activities such as interaction, information retrieval, collaboration of users etc. (Campbell, et. al 2011). Social media and networking sites have now become an integral part of our lives. The social networks have become a multipurpose tool for accessing various products and order them right from the comfort of one's home. Social media plays a vital role in engaging the customers to purchase a product. The business and industries are regarded to keep in mind the needs of the customer for the better utilization of their product. Therefore, it is important to understand how to utilize the social media as per the business and

needs of the clients (Mangold and Faulds 2009). Consumerism and social media are deeply connected with each other. Social media paves the way for the consumers to reach out to their desired products and also better access the resources in a new way. Technology driven developments, rise of mobile phones, social networks and peer to peer communication is increasing and impacting the consumer's day to day life (Shankar, et.al). Shopping has become easy for customers who use social media and it also aids in the growth of the sellers or companies in numerous ways (Cha, 2009). India is a diverse country with people with diverse needs, hence social media helps the companies to gain knowledge about their customer's needs. Even the companies are modifying their policies in such a way that more people get connect with social network and utilizes their range of services (Cha, 2009). Therefore, social media is an effective place to promote their products and attract potential customers. By the means of shopper marketing the products can be improved, clear messages can be delivered and brand promoters can be identified (Shankar et. al 2011). Social media has eventually created vast consumer communities which in many ways are helping the companies to build consumer interaction and interface thereby leading to sharing of information on the brand products. For example, there are many virtual brand communities which have created a space (computer generated) for their retailers and consumers so that they connect with each other. Social media has shaped a new culture of communication with the help of the social space Web 2.0. (Pookulangara and Koesler 2011). The understanding and insights are well developed by the means of social media because it helps to filter the opinion of the individuals (Cox, 2010). The retailers should always remain aware and conscious about the cultural background of the consumers and also know the importance. The cultural background of the consumers also triggers the attitude and opinion of the consumers for the formulation of a product or brand. (Cox, 2010). According to Cox, there is a strong correlation between the age of the consumers and their attitude. The format of the blogs, posts, videos in the social media are formulated into different formats which reach their target audience. For example, the people falling in the age group of 18-24 years have a strong liking towards a product say for educational items, fashion etc. However, the age group of 34-38 years may have a liking for some other products which suits them. Therefore, it is one of the major benefits of social media which helps the user catch their products as per their likings and similarities. The marketing arena transform in the shopping culture and marketing style 'Marketing 4.0' calls for a shift from simply using traditional means to more digital approaches to reach customers and develop customer relationships (Kotler et al., 2016).

Problem of Study

In the system of emerging market, the study of strategic policy of reputed company's products and infusing factors of social media on consumer shopping habits is the main problem of the study, it will be tried to find out how online marketing is sponsoring buying practices challenges and nature. In the context of this study the following objectives have been formulated

Object of Study Under the proposed research work, the following objectives have been formulated for a meaningful test for scientificity of the study.

1. To Study about impact of social media on shopping habit of consumer.
2. To examine about factors affecting social media on consumer culture.

Hypothesis of the Study

Research questions have been formulated to achieve logical and scientific impact of social media providing the direction to analyzed the marketing environment with consumer habit in a logical manner on the basis of scientificity.

Therefore, the following research question has been formulated in relation to the control of the limitation of the study

- 1 There is direct relation between social media and consumerism.
- 2 Does social media influences consumer culture?

Discussion

Communication is a medium to express emotions and not just an expression of ideas and thoughts. It is the most dynamic and oriented option in the development and progress of a society. The unimaginable changes in the field of communication and technology after the Industrial revolution have worked to promote consumerist culture in the society. Electronic and social media have transformed the way communication is performed today.

Social Media Landscape

Picture source - www.bing.com

Till, the 1990s the internet was not in vogue; however, the muddle of social networks began in the new millennium of 2000s where the first social media site was launched. Before that the product promotion went other electronic and print medium e-mails and through other referral strategies such as television, radio, newspapers etc. Social media is a group of internet-based applications that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content. The purpose of it is to create such interactive platform which is easily accessible to the public. Through web 2.0 to 3.0 social media has rapidly changed the world and that is how the industries are adopting to the vast changing technologies for the promotion of their products. Nowadays, the use of social media in the field of marketing is a common phenomenon. The largest social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, YouTube has engrossed the common man into its web. However, the pros and cons are discussed as to how the social media has played its role in the promotion of consumerism in the changing paradigm. Consumerism is a trend based on the belief that consuming more and owing more things leads to greater pleasure in this process social-media is catalyst in consumer buying behavior, shopping culture and Marketing 4.0. To promote the product in market pace and space with shaped P's of internet marketing i.e. product, price, place, promotion, personalization, social media attracts customers by strategic sales promotion technique and also harmonizing customer relation with company. Social media influencers are increasingly employed as product endorsers, and a growing body of academic research confirms that influencers are an effective advertising instrument that perceived credibility of the influencer and identification with the influencer mediate these relationships

The anatomy of social media splits in three divisions or ages: the Age of Electronic Communications (late 1960s to early 1990s), the Age of Virtual Community (early 1990s to early 2000s), and the era of

social media (early 2000s till date) explore the internationalization of online services publicly the growth and richness of participation on the Usenet system helped inspire the work of early ethnographers of the Internet. Age of Virtual Community, advanced Corporate and news sites like Amazon, Netflix, TripAdvisor, and all became recognizable hosts for peer-to-peer contact and conversation. In business and academia, a growing emphasis on ‘virtual community’ crystallizing the tendency of online life or community as an evolving cultural changes.

The cyclone of social media is making India rapidly a global digital energy house. By the year 2023, businesses need to stay ahead of the curve and understand the latest digital marketing trends to keep up with the competition. It has transformed the way to communicate, connect and consume. In the digital age, social media has become an integral part of our daily lives, and India is no exception. The Digital 2023 India report provides valuable insights into the usage of social media platform by people in India, which can be beneficial for businesses looking to expand their digital marketing efforts. According to the report, there were 467.0 million social media users in India in January 2023, which is equivalent to 32.8% of the total population. This number is expected to increase to 580 million by 2023, representing a growth rate of 29% over the next three years. The report also highlights that there were 398.0 million social media users aged 18 and above in India at the start of 2023, which is equivalent to 40.2% of the total population aged 18 and above. This indicates that social media platform is an important platform for businesses looking to connect with their target audience. Report reveals that 67.5% of India’s total internet user uses at least one social media platform in January 2023 also 73.5% of social media users in India were male, while 26.5% were female that indicates it is an ideal platform for businesses to engage with customers and build their brand equity.

Fig.1: Social media market share by platform (2023)

(Source:www.fitsmallbusiness.com)

In the present situation, social media is being used as a factor in getting exposed to excessive advertisements through social media to buy more products. Performances by celebrities boost popularity that influence shopping behavior. Due to the influence of social media, it affects human thinking and understanding, logical thinking. The audience also consumes inauthentic things by being sensitive for brand loyalty, show off, follow up trends.

Social media has positive effects on consumer mind that promote social interaction and connectedness, self-satisfaction, respect, growth, emotional expression that leads to the desire and need to consume. It also shapes the cultural values of consumer (one dimensional communication - behavior dissatisfaction is null) and monetary attitudes that influence consumers buying decisions, as well as establish the concept of rational commodity consumption by sacrificing for next best alternatives. The company has to consider 7'C of internet marketing while developing their strategy for market penetration in such target messaging contract, convenience, concentration, content, community, construction and commerce that resonates with both male and female audiences.

The following points depict the role of social media in consumerism such as:

Promotion : The traditional media such as newspapers, magazines, radio and television were used to promote a product and attract a customer which led to an increase in the consuming process. Nowadays social media spontaneously lure customers and therefore the purchasing process has become even more rapid as virtual community is much larger in space.

Product development: The virtual community is a large space where millions of people gather and share their views. The social media applications help the companies or manufacturing agencies to develop and design a particular product by the means of reviews also. The reviews of the customers help the companies to design and develop a product in a particular way so that their demand is fulfilled thereby supply of that particular product increases.

Purchase Intention: The passion to purchase products on social media are in habits and in trends. Instagram by which people gain followers and followings respectively. Therefore, it has increased the usage of consumers also influencing them to purchase different products that are either displayed by a celebrity or show off or any renowned company.

Customer's Awareness: Customer's awareness is a not a new concept, by the means of social media the customers are readily aware of what and how they buy. Therefore, when things come on public platforms

such as through tweets, mentions, likes, comments and sharing of content it creates a sense of awareness among the users of a particular product. A recent example of olaplex treatment which created a ruckus among users because it had a severe effect on the kidneys and was therefore banned in the European union.

Status Symbol : Social media has created a sense of individualism among people, hence, now people are purchasing more and more products as per their suitability. It has also created a sense of independence among consumers and now they can achieve better what they desire.

Creation of Demand : Social media is a mechanical process for demand creation. According to the theory of J.M Keynes demand creates its own supply, applied in the process of consumerism also. The social media amplifies new demand which leads to the increase in supply chain. With the increase in social problems, the demand for different products is created also increases the propensity to consume. Social media is used for novel demand creation strategies in order to market different brands to the customers. By the means of storytelling, podcasts and visual-graphics it helps to touch the target audience so that their need is fulfilled.

Attractive Products : In such a scenario social media grabs the attention of the consumers and paves the way for them to purchase incessantly. For example, the extravagant shows of the celebrities and social media influencers also lure the customers to purchase a particular product even if it is highly expensive or off the budget. Therefore, social media has also become a status symbol for individuals and therefore more and more people are accessing the networking sites in order to flaunt. The persistent desire to purchase and the want to remain in the fashion makes the consumers do unnecessary purchasing.

Advertisement through social media: Social media acts as a versatile tool to generate a good amount of customer traffic by the means of attractive advertisement. Also, it is a difficult task to approach the customers and mobilize them for which social media plays a pivotal role. The shopping tendency, purchasing capacity, consumption becomes easier when social media comes into role by placing desired product in fascinating manner on websites via click bug, RSS feed, attachment, advertisement slicing, optimization. Consumer are fussy and fastidious and their mind can be accelerated by marketer through push or pull technique of marketing that increase the buying behavior.

Company- Customer (C-C) relationship: Social media helps to build better customer-organization relationship via post purchase behavior, feedback, after sales services. The social media pages benefit the

customers and attract them regarding a particular product also leading to their branding. Customers usually rely on reliable sources, for instance if any product or its ingredients are mentioned on “X” (twitter), it hugely impacts the customers and intensifies their buying capacity by tactics of hatch tag, like, share.

Ease of access: By the means of social media the consumers get a better access to their favorite’s companies. Social media paves the way for not only being connected to the family and friends but also let the consumer access and reach out to the products they prefer. For example, organic products such as shampoos, hair-oils and other skin creams are now being on sale as many consumers purchase it as per their suitability.

Brand Transparency: New media platforms allow consumers to scrutinize with other brands and their practices on different websites provides greater transparency and accountability of products. For Ex cloths can be purchased at categorized at mantra compare to others competitive online companies where brands shape size can be analyzed in respect of quality shape, size, colour and logo that effect the buying habit.

Peer Influence: Social media has amplified the power of peer influence. recommendations and reviews from friends, family, and online communities with links, remarks, feedback that insect individual mind to use and purchase of products hence increase purchasing tendency.

Customer convenient: Social media and networking sites can easily solve the problems related to the daily life of a person that is being in isolation or found of entertainment as well as website search. For instance, if a customer is confused about which brand one should use for the treatment of hair and skin problems, they can readily connect themselves with the social media applications of the company and interact with them. Moreover, the customers can also go through reviews and virtual community posts for the access of better information, diversion of mind from isolation to entertainment. However, right marketing strategy would lead the brands and eventually solve the problems of the customers.

Social media has fundamentally reshaped consumer behavior and directly effecting marketing mix, creating a dynamic and interconnected landscape where information, influence and purchasing priority decisions also profoundly transformed consumer culture, impacting how consumer discover, evaluate, and purchase products and services.

Product Research: Consumers have instant access to vast amounts of information about products and services through online reviews, comparisons, and forums. This empowers them to make informed decisions for the same product line and offers with consumers expecting quick access to information, products, and services.

Targeted Advertising: Brands leverage sophisticated targeting tools to reach specific demographics and interest groups with tailored ads, increasing the chances of product discovery among potential customers.

Authenticity & Relatability: Consumers often trust influencers they relate to, making their recommendations more impactful than traditional advertising.

Reviews & Ratings: Social media platforms host a wealth of user-generated content, including reviews, ratings, and testimonials. These provide social proof, influencing purchasing decisions as consumers tend to trust the opinions of their peers.

Brand Communities: Brands cultivate online communities where customers connect, share experiences, and express their loyalty. These communities foster a sense of belonging and reinforce brand affinity that's create strong desires and connection relating to the products, places or services.

Lifestyle & Aspiration: Social media showcases curated lifestyles and aspirational content, influencing consumer desires and shaping trends. Users often emulate the lifestyles and products they catch online concerning favorite people and places that provides optimum satisfaction.

Cultural Trends: Social media acts as a catalyst for cultural trends, with viral challenges, hashtags, and memes rapidly spreading and influencing consumer behavior as status symbol or part of happiness and effected with follow up culture.

Shop-ability: Many social media platforms have integrated e-commerce features, allowing users to discover and purchase products directly within the app and websites. These streamlines buying process and encourages impulse purchases in a convenient way for personalized products.

Two-way Communication: Social media facilitates direct communication between brands and consumers. Brands can gather feedback, address concerns, and engage with their audience in real-time. Social media platforms are increasingly used for customer service, with brands providing support and resolving issues through direct messages or public posts.

Challenges and Considerations:

Misinformation & Manipulation: The spread of misinformation and manipulative marketing tactics can erode consumer trust and lead to misguided purchasing decisions and product orientation.

Privacy Concerns: The collection and use of user data for targeted advertising raise privacy concerns and ethical considerations. FOMO (fear of missing out), prompting consumers to make purchases quickly. Auto filled data are distracting and creates fear of misuse of personal information.

Mental Health Impacts: The curated and unrealistic portrayals of lifestyles, pictures videos links on social media can contribute to feelings of inadequacy, anxiety, and depression among users that glitches the cultural legacy hence resist to online search and use of social website search.

Social media has become an integral part of consumer culture, reshaping how we discover, interact with, and purchase products and services. It has empowered consumers with information and choice while also presenting challenges related to misinformation, privacy, and mental health. As social media continues to evolve, its role in shaping consumer behavior will likely only grow stronger. New media has revolutionized consumer behavior, empowering consumers with information, choice, and connectivity. Brands need to adapt to these changes by embracing digital channels, engaging with consumers authentically, and providing personalized experiences. As new media continues to evolve, its impact on consumer behavior will only grow stronger.

Research Methodology

Research is systematic deliberate and scientific enquire of a specific problem for a novel cause. Research undertaken to help solve specific marketing problems.

Data Collection

Two types of sources will be used to collect the facts of the proposed research work, the details of which are as follows-

Primary Data - Randomly chosen observation and responses of customers has been collected.

Secondary Data - Various literature books magazine journal has been taken into account for brief history and background of social media are encountered.

Methods

Descriptive study is used to state the interference the study problem.

Finding and suggestions

Therefore, the resultant behavior of social media has become deeply embedded in the lives of the consumers and acting as life blood of modern, fussy and fastidious customers in solving their problems in many ways side by side keeping touched with another world. However, it should be focused about what sort of efforts can be put for the better use of social media into promoting better consumer interests and improving their buying capacities, product development and surviving in the perfect competition. Consumerism ensures the interests of the society along with consumer welfare, but excessive exploitation of resources is a matter of concern in the coming future that can affect the environment and the coming generations sustainability. Marketing is unflinching activities, marketer have responsibility of cultural legacy by its (Cultural Social Responsibility) sustainability, consumption trends as well as provides economies of scale with rationality.

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